

Synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some pyrazoline derivatives of 4(3*H*)-quinazolinones

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The present communication describes the synthesis and antimicrobial activity of some new 6,8-disubstituted-2-(phenyl/methyl)-3-[4-(3-methyl-5-pyrazolinon-1-yl)carbonyl]phenyl/benzyl/methyl]-4(3*H*)-quinazolinones.

In view of the broad spectrum biological activities of quinazolinones¹ and pyrazolinones², we have synthesized some new compounds incorporating both the quinazolinone and pyrazolinone ring systems.

The parent compounds 6,8-disubstituted-2-(methyl/phenyl)-3-[4-(carboxyl)-substituted]-4(3*H*)-quinazolinones³ (2a-j) were prepared by the reaction of 2-substituted-

benzoxazinones (1a-j) with diverse aminocarboxylic acids. Compounds 2a-j were further transformed into their respective esters (3a-j) through the acid chlorides. These esters (3a-j), in turn reacted with hydrazine hydrate to afford the respective hydrazides (4a-j). The hydrazides (4a-j) underwent smooth cyclization with ethyl acetoacetate to give the title compounds.

Y	R	X	Y	R	X
5a	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄	f	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₂
b	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄	g	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₂
c	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄	h	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₂
d	CH ₃	C ₆ H ₄	i	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₂
e	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₄ -CH ₂	j	CH ₃	CH ₂

Antibacterial activity of compounds **5a-j** was evaluated against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Bacillus pumilus* using cup-plate method⁴ in methanol in the concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ using erythromycin as a reference drug. Compounds **5d**, **5g** and **5h** exhibited good antibacterial activity. The antifungal activity of the quinazolinones was evaluated by cup-plate method against *Aspergillus niger* at a concentration of 500 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ using nystatin as a reference drug. Compounds **5g**, **5h** and **5i** exhibited moderate antifungal activity.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined in open capillary and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 157 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Varian EM 360 spectrophotometer using TMS as an internal standard. Purity of the compounds was checked on silica gel G plates using iodine vapor as visualizing agent.

6,8-Disubstituted-2-(methyl/phenyl)-3-[4-(carboxyl)-substituted]-4(3*H*)-quinazolinones (**2a-j**) were synthesized by the reaction of various 2-substituted-benzoxazinones (**1**) with diverse aminocarboxylic acids by the reported methods³.

2-Phenyl-3-(p-carboethoxyphenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinones (3a) : 2-Phenyl-3-[4(carboxy)phenyl]-4(3*H*)-quinazolinone (**2a**; 0.01 mol) was refluxed with excess of thionyl chloride for 3 h. Excess thionyl chloride was then distilled off and cooled to room temperature. To this solution, absolute ethanol was added and refluxed for 3 h, then cooled and poured in cold water. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol as white crystals (60%), m.p. 157–158°. Similarly, other derivatives (yields 60–70%) were obtained : **3b**, m.p. 143–145°; **c**, 99–101°; **d**, 108–110°; **e**, 165–167°; **f**, 127–129°; **g**, 249–251°; **h**, 102–104°; **i**, 125–127°; **j**, 148–150°.

Conversion of 3a into the hydrazide (4a) : To a hot solution of **3a** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), hydrazine hydrate (90%; 0.02 mol) was added slowly with stirring and subsequently the reaction mixture was kept under reflux for 6 h. The solvent was then removed by distillation under reduced pressure and the residue dried and crystallized from ethanol as colorless crystals (76%), m.p. 172–173° (Found : C, 7.38; H, 4.49; N, 15.58. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_4\text{O}_2$ calcd. for : C, 70.58; H, 4.79; N, 15.68%); ν_{max} 3410 (NH₂), 3280 (NH), 1680 cm^{-1} (C=O).

Similarly, other derivatives (yields 75–85%) were obtained : **4b**, 178–180°; **c**, 108–110°; **d**, 62–64°; **e**, 154–156°; **f**, 178–180°; **g**, 225–227°; **h**, 130–132°; **i**, 140–142°; **j**, 214–216°.

2-Phenyl-3-[(4-(3-methyl-5-pyrazolinone-1-yl)carboxylphenyl)]-4(3H)-quinazolinones (5a) : To a solution of

the hydrazides (**4a**; 0.001 mol) in ethanol, ethyl acetoacetate (0.001 mol) was added and it was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. Excess solvent was then distilled off and set aside. The resulting solid was crystallized from ethanol to give **5a** (80%), m.p. 219–220° (Found : C 70.92; H, 4.26; N, 13.17. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 71.08; H, 4.29; N, 13.26%); ν_{max} 1690 (C=O), 1600 cm^{-1} (C=N); δ (CDCl₃/TMS) 7.23–8.38 (13H, m, ArH), 1.38 (2H, t, CH₂), 3.91 (3H, s, CH₃). Similarly, **5b-j** were prepared from **4b-j** : **5b** (80%), m.p. 183–184° (Found : C, 51.38; H, 2.48; N, 9.47. $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{16}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 51.75; H, 2.78; N, 9.66%); ν_{max} 1680 (C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); **c** (85%), 97–98° (Found : C, 66.58; H, 4.38; N, 15.39. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 66.66; H, 4.48; N, 15.55%), ν_{max} 1670 (C=O), 1610 cm^{-1} (C=N); **d** (84%), 71–72° (Found : C, 46.21; H, 2.52; N, 10.66. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 46.36; H, 2.72; N, 10.81%); **e** (75%), 151–152° (Found : C, 71.41; H, 4.51; N, 12.71. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 71.55; H, 4.60; N, 12.84); **f** (78%), 139–141° (Found : C, 52.45; H, 3.01; N, 9.23. $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{18}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 52.55; H, 3.05; N, 9.43%); **g** (80%), 128–130° (Found : C, 47.21; H, 2.92; N, 10.41. $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 47.39; H, 3.03; N, 10.53%); **h** (85%), 110–111° (Found : C, 66.48; H, 4.28; N, 15.19. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 66.66; H, 4.48; N, 15.55%); **i** (90%), 254–255° (Found : C, 46.21; H, 2.42; N, 10.68. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{Br}_2\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 46.36; H, 2.72; N, 10.81%); **j** (85%), 190–191° (Found : C, 60.32; H, 4.59; N, 18.61. $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{14}\text{N}_4\text{O}_3$ calcd. for : C, 60.40; H, 4.73; N, 18.78).

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